

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF POLYMERIC MATRIX COMPOSITES IN BIAXIAL STRESS FIELDS

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S U M M A R Y

A constitutive model on lamina level is developed for polymer composites, enabling to describe kinetic coupling effects between longitudinal, transverse and shear directions. It is derived from Schapery's thermodynamics based theory and thus incorporates a time-stress-superposition principle. The model is therefore particularly useful as a tool to predict long term mechanical properties from experimentally obtained short term properties.

Creep data to validate the model are generated on two test geometries: thin-walled cylindrical specimen, loaded in tension-torsion and the widely used off-axis coupon. Stress-interaction between the shear and transverse direction is entirely controlled by the average octahedral shear stress in the matrix. A parameter, consisting of a weighted sum of average octahedral matrix shear stress and fiber stress, is necessary to describe longitudinal-shear interaction. Due to this fact, the 10 degree off-axis coupon is not suitable for pure shear characterization. A 30 degree coupon is recommended for this purpose, as its response is least affected by the presence of other stress components.

1 INTRODUCTION

Matrix dominated mechanical properties of polymer based composite laminates are time dependent or viscoelastic and are sensitive to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity. Because of this fact, the long term integrity of a composite structural component is an important consideration in the initial design process. The manner in which viscoelastic matrix dominated properties vary with time over the design life time is an essential input to the design study. Accelerated characterization procedures, aiming at predicting long term composite behaviour under sustained loads, from short term test results, have been proposed by Brinson and coworkers [1]. The short term tests, required for the procedure, generally comprise one hour creep, 10 hours recovery testing of 3 off-axis coupons (0° , 90° and 10° for in plane shear characterization). Creep testing at several stress levels then allows to construct master curves, valid for one particular loading condition. Finally, classical lamination theory is used to obtain creep and creep-rupture predictions of general laminates. Improvements of the method have been accomplished during 10 years of research Hiel [2] emerged the whole procedure into an analytical framework, using a thermodynamics based nonlinear viscoelastic theory, which has been proposed by Schapery [3].

It is clear that a unidirectional ply in a laminate, which is used as a structural element will generally be subjected to a biaxial stress state (in the context of classical lamination theory), even if the overall applied stress is uniaxial. In order to improve the predictive capabilities of the accelerated testing method therefore a modelization of coupling effects be-

tween the longitudinal, transverse and shearing direction seems needed. This study aims at identifying and quantifying the effect of an imposed biaxial stress field on the time dependent nonlinear behaviour of unidirectionally reinforced composite materials.

2 THE CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

Since Schapery's theory incorporates a time-stress superposition principle in an analytical framework, it is very suitable for accelerated testing predictions of long term behaviour. It will therefore be used as a basis for the development of a behavioural law, incorporating kinetic coupling. The three-dimensional constitutive relations, as derived by Schapery from irreversible thermodynamical principles can be written as :

$$\epsilon_{ij} = - \frac{\partial G_R}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} + \frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{kl}}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} \int_{-\infty}^{\psi} \Delta S_{klmn} (\psi - \psi') \frac{d(\hat{\sigma}_{mn}/a_G)}{d\psi'} d\psi' \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_{ij} : components of the infinitesimal strain tensor

σ_{ij} : components of the stress-tensor

$G_R(\sigma_{ij}, T)$: the constant term of the Gibb's free energy

$\hat{\sigma}_{kl}$: nonlinearizing functions of σ_{ij} and absolute temperature T

ΔS_{klmn} : elements of the material transient compliance matrix

ψ : a reduced time, defined by

$$\psi = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a_G} \quad (2)$$

a_G : a nonlinearizing function of σ_{ij} and T (the shift factor)

a_G : a nonlinearizing function of σ_{ij} and T

Equations (1) do not involve any material symmetry considerations. An element of a lamina, as depicted in figure 1 however exhibits transversely isotropic symmetry in the (2, 3)-plane. The fiber direction is parallel with axis 1.

Figure 1.: transversely isotropic material element (the shear direction 12 is denoted by 6 in the text)

Experimental creep compliance curves, obtained over a limited time frame $(0, t_a)$ for different applied stress states can be shifted horizontally as well as vertically to yield one master curve, characteristic for a particular stress field. The shift factors are functionally related to the imposed stress field through the use of a suitable invariant.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The validity of the set of model equations (3) was checked by performing creep-recovery tests on two distinct specimen geometries. Thin-walled cylinders with reinforcing fibers oriented axially as well as transversely were loaded in combined tension-torsion, allowing the coverage of a large variety of transverse/longitudinal-shear stress combinations. These experiments were supplemented with familiar off-axis coupon tension tests, where all three plane stress components are necessarily present, their relative magnitude being controlled by the fiber angle with respect to the loading axis.

A graphite epoxy system (60 % of fiber volume) was used as test material, consisting of T300 carbon fibers, embedded in a Shell epicote 828 epoxy resin. All samples were postcured according to the following scheme: heatup from room temperature to 125°C at an average rate of 1°C/min, constant temperature of 125°C for 2 hours, cool down from 125°C to room temperature at a rate of 0.25°C/min. They were subsequently stored in a desiccator to avoid absorption of moisture. Prior to each creep-recovery cycle all samples were cyclicly conditioned until a reproducible response was attained. Samples were strain-gauged back to back with micro-measurements WR-350 rosettes. An MTS-systems dynamical tension-torsion machine was used as loading device. All experimental results, reported here were obtained at a temperature of 65°C. Experimentally obtained creep-recovery curves in the linear range were fitted by a power law. Using this function yields for creep-recovery loading in the nonlinear range:

$$\epsilon_{ij}^c = \left[g_0(\Sigma) S_{ij}^0 + \frac{g_1(\Sigma) g_2(\Sigma)}{a_\sigma^n(\Sigma)} S_{ij} t^n \right] \sigma_j \quad 0 < t \leq t_a \quad (5a)$$

$$\epsilon_{ij}^r = \frac{\Delta \epsilon_{ij}}{g_1(\Sigma)} \left[(1 + a_\sigma(\Sigma) \lambda)^n - (a_\sigma(\Sigma) \lambda)^n \right] \sigma_j \quad t_a \leq t < t_b \quad (5b)$$

where $\Delta \epsilon_{ij} = g_1 g_2 S_{ij} \left(\frac{t_a}{a_\sigma} \right)^n$ and $\lambda = \frac{t - t_a}{t_a}$ (5c)

Nonlinearizing functions a_σ and g_1 are readily obtained by fitting the recovery response (5b), while a fit of the creep response (5a) yields the remaining functions g_0 and g_2 .

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tension tests on 0 degree coupons and cylindrical specimen under a great variety of stress states confirmed a linear elastic behaviour of the graphite epoxy material in the fiber direction. A small stiffening effect of an additional imposed shear stress on the time independent response of tubes in the fiber direction occurred. This behaviour however is of purely geometri-

cal origin and is discussed in another paper [5].

A weak but definite viscoelastic response was noted in the transverse direction. In pure tension this time dependence did not show any sign of non-linearity during two hour creep deformation at transverse stresses up to 30 MPa (90% of the ultimate stress in the transverse direction). Nonlinearities however became apparent when applying an additional shear stress. Figure 2 shows a series of creep compliance curves at a moderate transverse stress σ_2 of 14 MPa, for different compliance ratios of shear to transverse stress. The dots represent experimental data points, the model fit is given by the solid lines. Shear stress strongly enhances the observed creep rate in the transverse direction.

Figure 2 : Transverse creep compliance vs. log time for several shear stress to transverse stress ratios.

The viscoelastic response in shear was always nonlinear except for pure shear stress levels below about 9 MPa. This is illustrated in figure 3, which shows a series of pure shear compliance curves at shear stress levels up to 42 MPa, obtained on pure torsion loaded 0 degree tubes.

Shear stress does appear to trigger mechanisms, essentially nonlinear in nature, which manifest themselves both in the transverse and shear direction.

Figure 3 : 0 degree tube shear compliances vs.log time

Creep kinetics in shear are affected by transverse stresses as well but to a much lesser extent. This is illustrated in figure 4 where an increase in transverse stress of 200 % is seen to yield shear creep strains after 3600 sec of creep deformation, which are typically 7 % higher than in pure shear loading.

Figure 4 : shear compliance at a fixed shear of 20 MPa for combined transverse-shear loading (90 degree cylinder)

This points to the average octahedral matrix shear stress as the prime con-

trolling factor of kinetic coupling between the transverse and shear direction. Using Hill's concentration factors yields for the present material :

$$T_{\text{oct}}^m = \frac{1}{3} [0.71\sigma_2^2 + 8.46T_{12}^2]^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

Of course, the calculation of average stresses in the matrix is based on an elastic solution, and thus might only give a rough estimation of actual matrix stresses. At high imposed stress levels portions of the matrix will undoubtedly be in a plastic state. Moreover, viscoelastic effects might strongly interfere with this local yielding. It might be hypothesized however, that all these effects will tend to smoothen out local matrix stresses. The average constant matrix stresses, as calculated from Hill's model, therefore probably give a good estimation of actual matrix stresses.

As far as the model (3) is concerned, most nonlinearity turned out to be contained in the shift function a_σ . The other nonlinearizing parameters g_0, g_1 and g_2 only showed minor deviations from their linear value of 1, when increasing the stress field magnitude. Figure 5 exemplifies typical variations of these functions for a 90 degree tube loaded in pure torsion. The same weak variations were encountered in combined stress states.

Figure 5 : shear stress dependence of the nonlinearizing functions g_0, g_1 and g_2 for pure torsion on 90 degree cylinders.

A typical variation of a_σ vs. the stress state invariant T_{oct}^m for combined $(\sigma_2 - T_{12})$ loading is depicted in figure 6. Using T_{oct}^m as a stress intensity parameter clearly groups all data points in different directions around a common data fit:

$$a_\sigma = 2,78 \exp(-0.094 T_{\text{oct}}^m) \quad (7)$$

Figure 6 : Nonlinearizing shift factor a_σ vs. average octahedral matrix stress for pure shear and combined transverse stress-shear stress.

Stress interaction between the longitudinal and shear directions was studied on small angle off-axis coupons. Experiments on thin-walled 0 degree cylinders, loaded in combined tension-torsion were also performed. Their response however was overshadowed by geometrical effects. The correlation between the latter and results, obtained on the off-axis coupons is the subject of another paper [5]. In this study we will confine ourselves to the off-axis coupon results.

The deficiency of T_{oct}^m to describe longitudinal-shear kinetic coupling is clearly demonstrated when comparing creep compliance curves of off-axis coupons for the same value of the resolved octahedral matrix stress (figure 7)

Figure 7: Comparison of 3 off-axis coupon creep compliances for an average matrix octahedral shear stress value of 20 MPa

Higher creep rates are obtained in small angle off-axis configurations. This points to a large influence of the resolved fiber stress σ_1 on creep kinetics in shear. Investigations of yielding phenomena in polymeric solids have demonstrated that the isotropic component of the stress field alters the conditions and type of yielding that are observed. Moreover, biaxial stress relaxation studies on glassy PMMA in combined tension-torsion strain fields, as reported by Sternstein and HO [6], identified the mean normal strain, and not the octahedral strain, as the principle factor governing both the effect of strain field on relaxation kinetics and the onset of nonlinear viscoelastic behaviour. Although local stress fields in the composite are considerably different from those existing in the bulk polymer for the same macroscopically induced forces, this would indicate the importance of mean normal stress in controlling yield phenomena. However, inclusion of the average matrix normal stress to describe the present data, would greatly over estimate the influence of the transverse stress σ_2 , which contributes a major portion to the first invariant of the matrix stress field. Highly nonlinear behaviour would then result in the transverse direction, which is negated by the results previously mentioned.

A parameter \hat{T} , equal to a weighted sum of the average octahedral matrix stress and the longitudinal fiber stress, was therefore considered :

$$\hat{T} = T_{\text{oct}}^m + \mu \sigma_1 \quad (8)$$

The phenomenological parameter μ represents the sensitivity of the observed nonlinear response to σ_1 . It would appear to be temperature dependent if σ_1 -enhanced local cracking and plastification of the matrix are assumed to be predominantly responsible for the increased creep rates. Using parameter \hat{T} as a measure of the local matrix stress field yielded a very good correlation with experimental results for all loading directions and combined stress state combinations. The invariant character however is apparently lost.

A last remark concerns the suitability of the 10 degree off-axis coupon for pure shear characterization. The experimental results generated point to a large influence of the imposed biaxial stress state (especially the fiber stress σ_1) on the shear response for this configuration. It should therefore not be used for pure shear characterization studies. Instead the 30 degree coupon is recommended. Our measurements indicated 30 degree coupon shear properties in excellent agreement with pure shear properties, as found from thin-walled tube testing.

5 REFERENCES

- 1 BRINSON, H.F., MORRIS, D.H. and YEOW, Y.T. - A new experimental method for the accelerated characterization of composite materials. VDI - Berichte 313, 1978, 395-400.
- 2 HIEL, C.C. - The nonlinear viscoelastic response of resin matrix composites, Ph. D. thesis, Free University of Brussels, 1983.
- 3 SCHAPERY, R.A. - A theory of nonlinear thermo viscoelasticity based on irreversible thermodynamics, Proc. V th U.S. Nat. Cong. of Appl. Mech., 511-530.

- 4 BROWER, H.R. - Nonlinear viscoelastic characterization of transversely isotropic fibrous composites under biaxial loading, Ph. D. thesis, Free University of Brussels, 1986.
- 5 BROWER, H.R. - Analysis of tubular composite elements, subjected to biaxial loading, Proc. ICCS-4, Paisley, 24-27 july 1987, ed. I.M. MARSHALL.
- 6 STERNSTEIN, S.S. and HO, T.C., Biaxial stress relaxation in glassy polymers : PMMA, J. Appl. Phys., vol. 43, 11, 1972, 4370-4383.